

Floral Phenological and Morphological Studies of Guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) Varieties under South Gujarat Condition

Roja H. S., Y. N. Tandel*, V. R. Zala, M. A. Patel,

Vipasha D. Dangariya and Surya S. Nair

ISSN: 1542-2666

NAAS Rating (2025): 5.00

<https://www.jarvm.co/index.html>

jarvm.submit@gmail.com

2025; 20-1(Part-B): 102-110

Received: 18-08-2025

Accepted: 12-09-2025

Roja H. S.,

Department of Fruit Science,
ASPEE College of Horticulture,
Navsari Agricultural University,
Navsari, 396450, Gujarat, India

Y. N. Tandel

Department of Fruit Science,
ASPEE College of Horticulture,
Navsari Agricultural University,
Navsari, 396450, Gujarat, India

V. R. Zala

Department of Fruit Science,
ASPEE College of Horticulture,
Navsari Agricultural University,
Navsari, 396450, Gujarat, India

M. A. Patel

Department of Fruit Science,
ASPEE College of Horticulture,
Navsari Agricultural University,
Navsari, 396450, Gujarat, India

Vipasha D. Dangariya

Department of Fruit Science,
ASPEE College of Horticulture,
Navsari Agricultural University,
Navsari, 396450, Gujarat, India

Surya S. Nair

Department of Fruit Science,
ASPEE College of Horticulture,
Navsari Agricultural University,
Navsari, 396450, Gujarat, India

*Corresponding author

Y. N. Tandel

Department of Fruit Science,
ASPEE College of Horticulture,
Navsari Agricultural University,
Navsari, 396450, Gujarat, India

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17104055

Abstract

Understanding the reproductive biology, genetic diversity, and evolutionary relationships of guavas depends on pollen characteristics and floral phenology. An analysis of six distinct guava cultivars-Yogi, Sanjari, Exotica, VNR 1 kg, Lalit, and Sardar (L-49) - was carried out in South Gujarat conditions to know the suitability of various guava cultivars for breeding programs. According to floral morphological observations, VNR Bihi had the most stamens, whereas Sardar had the biggest flower length, width, and number of petals. Anthesis occurred between 04:00 a.m. and 09:30 a.m., while pollen dehiscence was observed from 04:30 a.m. to 10:15 a.m. The stigma remained receptive for two days. Floral bud development progressed through eight distinct stages, from dormant bud to fully opened flower, requiring 34-42 days for completion. Lalit had the best pollen viability among the kinds, while Sardar (L-49) had the highest pollen germination.

Keywords: Phenology, Morphology, Bud development, Guava varieties, Pollen viability.

Introduction

Guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) is a prevalent allogamous fruit tree belonging to the Myrtaceae family and Magnoliopsida class. It is known as "Apple of Tropics" and "Poor Man's Apple," native to Tropical America and was introduced to India by the Portuguese in the 17th century. China, Thailand, Indonesia, Cuba, Brazil, and India are key guava growing countries, with India ranking it as the fourth most important fruit after mango, citrus, and banana. In India, guava occupying 3.07 lakh ha area and 45.16 lakh tonnes production. It's cultivation has been confined to the states of Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Rajasthan and Andhra Pradesh. In area and production, Uttar Pradesh stands first with an area of 0.52 lakh hectares and production 9.83 lakh tonnes while Andhra Pradesh stands first in productivity with 23 MT ha⁻¹. The area of guava in Gujarat is around 0.14 lakh hectares with production of 1.79 lakh million tonnes and 12.20 MT ha⁻¹ productivity. Approximately 20 of the 150 species in the *Psidium* genus produce edible fruits, with only 12 to 15 cultivars cultivated on a commercial scale. The fruit is valued for its year-round availability, nutritional content and suitability for processing. It's a source of vitamins A, B₁, B₂, C, lycopene and useful minerals like calcium, phosphorus, and iron. Guava finds uses in jams, jellies, and traditional medicines for treating diarrhoea and dysentery. The guava tree is hardy and can grow in varied climates, tolerating poor soils and limited irrigation. It flowers twice a year in North Indian conditions and yields more during the rainy season. Floral biology knowledge, including flowering behaviour, anthesis, flowering duration, receptivity of stigma, duration of anther maturity and anther dehiscence, pollen viability and pollen germination is vital for plant reproductive biology, taxonomy, breeding programs for successful hybridization. Research aimed at improving guava characteristics and addressing challenges. In conclusion, guava is a valuable fruit with broad cultivation and usage. Its adaptability, high nutritional value and year-round availability contribute to its popularity.

Understanding its biology and addressing challenges can lead to better cultivars and increased productivity.

Materials and Methods

The field experiment on flower biology of some guava varieties under South Zone of Gujarat during December, 2022 to June, 2024 under Gujarat condition was carried out at Regional Horticultural Research Station, Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari. The climate of the zone is tropical, i.e., humid and warm monsoon with heavy rainfall, moderately cold winter and fairly hot and humid summer. The average rainfall of the tract is more than 1500 mm and normally starts by June and ceases by September end. The experiment was laid out in completely randomised design (CRD) with four repetitions. The plants were three years old and planted at the distance of 3m x 2m spacing. There were six varieties viz., T₁- Yogi, T₂- Sanjari, T₃- Exotica, T₄- VNR Bihi, T₅- Lalit and T₆-Sardar (L-49).

Flower morphology

Five shoots of each variety were tagged in random and recorded the flowering habit i.e., either the flowers were born on the current season growth in the axils of leaves or terminal vegetative bud of the shoot. Further, the flower was solitary or in cymes of two or three was also recorded. Flower colour was observed visually as per colour chart of the Royal Horticulture Society, London (Edition, 2015). Flower type was noted visually as per the botanical classification. Average length (from tip to base) and width (at widest part) of five flowers measured was measured in centimetre with the help of scale at fully developed flower bud. Number of petals, sepals and stamens were recorded by counting in each genotype.

Days required for bud development

Duration of flower bud development was studied by dividing the whole bud development phase (bud swelling to calyx break stage) into eight arbitrary stages on the basis of the size of the flower buds. Two slender green bracteoles served as protection for the first stage (S-I). The

second stage bud (S-II) was attained in 7 to 9 days, where bud had conical shape with defined pedicel. In the third stage (S-III) a constriction in the middle of bud appeared in another 5 to 8 days. The buds reached the fourth stage (S-IV) in the following 5 to 6 days, at which point of constriction was more pronounced and clearly separated the ovarian section, which had spherical form. At fifth stage (S-V), the upper part began to more grow quickly and became round than the lower part in 4 to 5 days. The bud colour had stayed green up to sixth stage (S-VI) which attained in 4 to 6 days. In seventh stage (S-VII) buds were matured, attained maximum size and shape were distinctive during the course of 4 to 5 days. The splitting of the calyx, which occurred 13 to 26 hours before the flower open, denoted the eighth stage (S-VIII). The calyx split unevenly or split open like a cap.

The flower buds of the smallest to the largest size in each cultivar were collected. At three days interval, buds were studied in each cultivar to find the number of days required for passing from each stage to the next. The total number of days required from bud emergence to anthesis of each bud was recorded.

Anthesis period

Time taken for flower opening from calyx break stage was calculated in each genotype. The flower buds at calyx break stage were selected and tagged. The observations were made during anthesis period from 04:00 a.m. to 11:00 a.m. as suggested by Dinesh and Vasugi (2010).

Duration of stigma receptivity (days)

Receptivity of stigma was studied under controlled pollination conditions, where the buds were emasculated at appropriate stage of its development and pollinated with pollen grains collected from freshly opened flowers up to five days at one day interval. The pollinated flowers were tagged and bagged immediately. The fruit set was recorded after seven days of pollination and taken as an indication of receptivity (Sharma et al., 2013).

Duration of anther maturity (days)

Duration of anther maturity was computed by taking the flower buds of the smallest stage

(stage II) to the flower anther dehiscence stage in each cultivar and expressed as mean number of days.

Time of pollen dehiscence

Every day in morning hours the dehiscence of anthers was recorded by observing freshly opened flowers in each variety. When 25 to 50 per cent of the anthers had dehisced, the dehiscence was considered to have taken place. The period during which maximum flowers dehisced was noted. The observations were made from 04:00 a.m. to 11:00 a.m. in each cultivar (Sharma et al., 2013). When anthers became yellow in appearance in a flower, it was taken to have dehisced.

Duration of flowering (days)

Ten bearing shoots on each tree were tagged. Dates on which first and last flower opened, were recorded. Observations on the date of opening of first flower, date of opening of last flower and duration of flowering were noted.

Pollen germination (%)

Pollen germination was assessed with the hanging drop method. Pollen germination was determined by placing a small drop of germinating media on a cover glass and then pollen grains were sown on the drop by touching anther after completion of bursting and the cover glass was then inverted and rested on the cavity slide. Pollens were incubated under dark conditions at room temperature in a culture medium containing sucrose 100 g/l, boric acid 0.1 g/l, magnesium sulphate 0.2 g/l, potassium nitrate 0.1 g/l and calcium nitrate 0.3 g/l. The slides were incubated at 28 °C for 24-48 h for getting pollen tube growth. Pollen grains were considered germinated when pollen tube length was at least equal to or greater than the pollen diameter (Tanmoy et al., 2016).

$$\text{Pollen germination (\%)} = \frac{\text{No. of germinated pollen grains}}{\text{Total number of pollen grains}} \times 100$$

Pollen viability (%)

Acetocarmine staining procedure was used to determine the pollen grain viability. Pollen grains were examined under the microscope at

40 X. A viable pollen grain would absorb the dye and stained red, while non-viable pollens remain unstained.

Pollen viability was calculated as ratio of viable pollen to the total number of pollen grains and expressed in per cent (Tandel et al. 2024).

$$\text{Pollen viability (\%)} = \frac{\text{No. of viable pollen grains}}{\text{Total number of pollen grains}} \times 100$$

Result and Discussion

Flower morphology

The blooms were borne in the axil of the leaves of the current season growth. The flowers could be seen in cymes of two to three or alone. Both terminal and lateral stems were capable of bearing flowers and appeared dispersed. The flowering behaviour was consistent in all varieties throughout the experimental period. Lalit and VNR Bihi both exhibited lateral and terminal bearing habit, while other varieties had lateral bearing behaviour. Similar observations were also noted by Balasubrahmanyam (1959) and Sharma et al. (2017).

The floral colour of Sardar (L-49) was translucent and resembled transparent white in tone. The Sanjari and Yogi flowers had dull white colour. The Exotica flowers were in snowy white colour. The VNR Bihi blossom was pale in colour. Lalit had white coloured flowers with a golden tint. Flower type was hermaphrodite in all varieties of guava. The flower colour of all the varieties may be due to genetic constituents. The similar observations were noticed by Sandhu et al. (2024).

Mean flower length among all the varieties which ranged from 1.93 cm to 2.30 cm. Sardar had the longest average flower length (2.30 cm) followed by Yogi (2.16 cm), Lalit (2.11 cm), Sanjari (2.09 cm) and VNR Bihi (2.08 cm). Exotica flowers had the shortest average flower length (1.93 cm). Floral variation may have been a response to the shifting conditions of environment (Herrera, 2005). Similarly, maximum flower length in Sardar had been observed by Sandhu et al. (2024) and Bose et al. (2019).

Among guava varieties, Sardar had the largest flower width (4.98 cm), followed by Lalit (4.57 cm), Yogi (4.17 cm), Sanjari (4.13 cm) and VNR Bihi (4.02 cm). Exotica flowers had the smallest mean flower width (3.77 cm). Variation in bloom size is most likely to be polygenic. According to Galliot et al. (2006), the quantitative trait loci (QTL) with a significant impact on variation in floral size have also been found.

The average number of petals ranged from 4.22 to 8.85. Sardar (L-49) had the highest mean number of petals (8.85) followed by Sanjari, Yogi, Lalit and VNR Bihi, with mean numbers of 8.41, 7.62, 7.51, and 5.85, respectively. Exotica had the lowest average number of petals (4.22). There was no difference in number of flower sepal. In all varieties, the average number of sepals per flower was discovered to be four. It was also observed that different flowers on the same plant have different numbers of petals. Similarly, Sandhu et al. (2024) recorded six to nine petals in guava and also found no significant variation in the sepal numbers per flower and it was the same in all the guava cultivars.

Considerable variations were discovered among guava varieties for stamen counts. VNR Bihi (563.41) had the highest stamens per flower, followed by Sardar (490.48), Sanjari (424.60) and Lalit (421.30). Exotica had the lowest recorded number of stamens (390.83) followed by Yogi (390.99). The differences in flower size and number of stamens per flower in each cultivar might be due to genetic variation, agro-climatic condition and agronomic practices (Sharma et al. 2017). The findings were consistent with work of Sandhu et al. (2024) and Sharma et al. (2017).

Days required for bud development

The number of days required for the completion of one stage to another stage reduced progressively. The days required for full bud development were ranged between 34 to 42 days. VNR Bihi took maximum days (42) for bud development followed by Lalit (40 days), Sardar (39 days), Sanjari (36 days) Yogi (35 days) and Exotica (34 days).

The present investigation was similar with the work of Sharma et al. (2017) and Bose et al. (2019). The difference in the number of days for bud development might be due to agroclimatic conditions, annual climatic variation of the localities and varietal characters.

Anthesis Period

The first sign of unfolding of the floral bud was marked by the appearance of cracks at the apex of the bud, where the calyx lobes were united. The sepals gradually separated, exposing the crumpled petals which started bulging out. The sepals grew continuously by the pressure of the bulging petals inside, from the incurved form to straight and from straight to slightly to out-curve.

The anthesis was detected between 04:30 a.m. to 09:30 a.m. in all the varieties. Yogi and Sanjari displayed the earliest anthesis between 04:30 a.m. to 05:10 a.m. VNR Bihi had late anthesis

between 06:20 a.m. to 09:30 a.m. Whereas, other varieties were showed anthesis between 05:00 a.m. to 07:30 a.m.

The present investigation was also similar with the work of Alfia et al. (2017) and Vishwakarma et al. (2021) on different guava cultivars. Variation in the timing of anthesis may result from the combination of endogenous developmental cues and external stimuli that exercised some control over floral initiation, induction and anthesis (Wilkie, 2009); Reddy and Bhagwan (2014) noted that floral induction and anthesis depended more on temperature than photoperiod in many perennial crops. It may also be the result of cultivars responding differently to various geographic locations and period of time for a particular variety.

Table 1. Floral morphological attributes of different varieties of guava

Varieties	Flower position	Flower colour	Flower type	Flower length (cm)	Flower width (cm)	Number of petals	Number of sepals	Number of stamens
T₁: Yogi	Lateral	Dull white	Hermaphrodite	2.16	4.17	7.62	4	390.99
T₂: Sanjari	Lateral	Dull white	Hermaphrodite	2.09	4.13	8.41	4	424.60
T₃: Exotica	Lateral	Snow white	Hermaphrodite	1.93	3.77	4.22	4	390.83
T₄: VNR Bihi	Terminal and lateral	Pallid and dull white	Hermaphrodite	2.08	4.02	5.85	4	563.41
T₅: Lalit	Terminal and lateral	Yellowish white	Hermaphrodite	2.11	4.57	7.51	4	421.30
T₆: Sardar (L-49)	Lateral	Transparent-white	Hermaphrodite	2.30	4.98	8.85	4	490.48
S.Em. ±	-	-	-	0.0	0.09	0.20	-	9.48
C.D. at 5 %	-	-	-	0.13	0.26	0.60	-	28.17
C.V. %	-	-	-	4.22	4.24	5.76	-	4.24

Table 2. Phenological study of number of days taken from bud initiation to calyx break stage in guava varieties

S. No	Cultivars	No. of days required for passing from one stage to other								Total no. of days for bud development	Calyx break stage to full bloom (Days)	Full bloom to petal shed (days)
		S-I	S-II	S-III	S-IV	S-V	S-VI	S-VII	S-VIII			
1.	T₁: Yogi	-	8	6	5	4	4	4	4	35	1	1
2.	T₂: Sanjari	-	8	6	5	5	4	4	4	36	1	1
3.	T₃: Exotica	-	7	5	5	5	4	4	4	34	1	1
4.	T₄: VNR Bihi	-	9	8	6	5	5	5	4	42	1	1
5.	T₅: Lalit	-	9	6	5	5	5	5	4	40	1	1
6.	T₆: Sardar (L-49)	-	8	6	6	5	5	5	4	39	1	1

Table 3: Phenological variations in different varieties of guava flowers

Varieties	Anthesis period	Time of pollen dehiscence	Duration of anther maturity (days)	Duration of stigma receptivity (days)	Pollen germination (%)	Pollen viability (%)
T1: Yogi	4:45 -5:10 a.m.	5:00 -5:45 a.m.	27.85	2	69.42	88.96
T2: Sanjari	4:30 -5:00 a.m.	4:45 -5:30 a.m.	28.53	2	70.57	86.19
T3: Exotica	5:15 -6:30 a.m.	5:35 -6:45 a.m.	26.28	2	66.96	77.25
T4: VNR Bihi	6:20 -9:30 a.m.	7:00 -10:15 a.m.	33.53	2	58.16	71.39
T5: Lalit	5:30 -6:30 a.m.	6:00 -6:45 a.m.	31.74	2	79.21	93.83
T6: Sardar	5:00 -7:00a.m.	5:30 -7:30 a.m.	30.33	2	82.45	91.80
S.Em. ±	-	-	-	-	3.74	3.14
C.D. at 5 %	-	-	-	-	11.13	9.35
C.V. %	-	-	-	-	10.53	7.41

Table 4: Time and duration of flowering in different varieties of guava

Varieties	Duration of flowering		
	Initiation of flowering	End of flowering	Total number of days (mean)
T1: Yogi	15 Dec. to 17 Dec.	20 Jan. to 22 Jan.	36
T2: Sanjari	16 Dec. to 19 Dec.	23 Jan. to 26 Jan.	38
T3: Exotica	20 Dec. to 24 Dec.	23 Jan. to 27 Jan.	34
T4: VNR Bihi	01 Dec. to 03 Dec.	17 Jan. to 19 Jan.	47
T5: Lalit	10 Dec. to 13 Dec.	18 Jan. to 21 Jan.	39
T6: Sardar	05 Dec. to 08 Dec.	14 Jan. to 17 Jan.	40

Fig. 1. Bud development stages in guava varieties

Fig.2. Anthesis stages of guava varieties

Fig 3. Pollen germination of different varieties of guava

Fig 4. Pollen viability of different varieties of guava

Duration of stigma receptivity

It is observed that the peak stigma receptivity was found immediately following anthesis. The stigma receptivity was persisted for up to two days after the flowers opening in all varieties under study.

Duration of Anther Maturity

Average anther maturation days were maximum and minimum in VNR Bihi (33.53 days) and Exotica (31.74 days), respectively. Sardar, Sanjari, Yogi and Exotica took 30.33 days, 28.53 days, 27.85 days and 26.28 days, respectively for anther maturity. These variations were might be due to interactions between the genotypes and phenotypes of the varieties.

Time of Pollen Dehiscence

The perusal observation on time of pollen dehiscence revealed that dehiscence of pollens occurred between fifteen to thirty minutes after flower anthesis ranges between 04:45 a.m. to 10:15 a.m. in all varieties. Sanjari showed

earliest pollen dehiscence 04:45 a.m. to 05:30 a.m. VNR Bihi and Lalit exhibited late pollen dehiscence between 06:00 a.m. to 07:45 a.m. and 06:50 a.m. to 10:15 a.m., respectively. The pollen dehiscence timings in Yogi, Exotica, and Sardar were between 05:00 a.m. to 05:45 a.m., 05:35 a.m. to 6:45 a.m. and 05:30 a.m. to 07:30 a.m., respectively. According to Seth (1962), variation in anther dehiscence might be due to fluctuations in minimum temperature and humidity had a significant impact on anther when once dehiscence occurred. However, humidity had more impact than temperature which can significantly alter the pollen dehiscence.

Duration of Flowering (days)

Duration of blooming period varied with different guava varieties. Flowering period commenced between 1st week of December to the 4th week of January. VNR Bihi had the earliest and longest flowering period, lasting 47

days from 1st week of December to 3rd week of January. It was followed by Sardar (40 days from 1st week of December to 3rd week of January), Lalit (39 days from 2nd week of December to 3rd January) and Sanjari (38 days from 3rd December to 4th week of January). Exotica had the shortest flowering duration *i.e.*, 34 days from 4th week of December to last week of January. The climatic circumstances of a specific place have an impact on the timing and length of flowering, which was another varietal characteristic. As a result, locals, cultivars and flowering times all differ.

Pollen Germination (%)

The trend of pollen germination was kept in the following order: Sardar (82.45 %), Lalit (79.21 %), Sanjari (70.57 %), Yogi (69.42 %), Exotica (66.96 %) and VNR Bihi (58.16 %). The pollen germination might be varied with the location and media used during germination study. Similar results found in Vishwakarma et al. (2021).

Pollen Viability (%)

The pollen viability was recorded in the range of 71.39 per cent to 93.83 per cent. Taking into account of the six varieties, it was observed maximum pollen viability in Lalit (93.83 %) which was at par with Sardar (L-49) (91.80 %), Yogi (88.96 %) and Sanjari (86.19 %). VNR Bihi recorded the minimum pollen viability (71.39 %). Variation might be due to the genetic and environmental factors (Jha et al., 2020). There are many factors *viz.*, fertility of soil, climatic conditions, genetic constitution *etc.*

Conclusions

The findings of the present investigation led to the conclusion that the variety Sardar (L-49) was found to be predominant in the flower morphological characters, which will be considered in the future breeding programme.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to ASPEE College of Horticulture, Navsari, Gujarat for providing necessary facilities in carrying out the present investigation.

Funding Declarations

The authors have not disclosed any funding.

Conflict of interest

The authors have not disclosed any competing interests.

References

1. Alfia MA, Vasugi C, Honnabyraiah MK, Adiga JD, Shivapriya M, Vincent L (2017) Phenological stages of wild species and cultivated species of guava (*Psidium guajava* L.). *Int. J. Pure App. Biosci.* 5(6): 464-474. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.18782/2320-7051.5994>
2. Bose SK, Ahmed S, Howlader P, Ali M (2019) Flowering, fruiting behaviour and nutritional quality of selected guava genotypes. *Int. J. Hort. Sci. Tech.* 6(1): 11-25. DOI: 10.22059/ijhst.2019.276101.279
3. Dinesh MR, Vasugi C (2010) Guava improvement in India and future needs. *J. Hortic. Sci.* 5(2): 94-108. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.24154/jhs.v5i2.454>
4. Galliot C, Hoballah ME, Kuhlemeier C, Stuurman J (2006) Genetics of flower size and nectar volume in petunia pollination syndromes. *Planta.* 225 (1): 203-212. DOI: 10.1007/s00425-006-0342-9
5. Herrera J (2005) Flower size variation in *Rosmarinus officinalis*: individuals, populations and habitats. *Ann. Bot.* 9: 431-437. DOI: 10.1093/aob/mci041
6. Jha MK, Kumari P, Sengupta S, Rani R, Singh YK (2020) Study of pollen viability and pollen germination in different cultivars of litchi in Sabour, Bhagalpur condition. *J. Pharmacogn. Phytochem.* 9(2): 1312-1317. <http://www.phytojournal.com/archives/2020/vol9issue2/PartV/9-2-85-297.pdf>
7. Reddy YN, Bhagwan A (2014) Physiology of flowering in perennial fruit crops. In: *National Seminar Cum Workshop. Induction of flowering in fruit crops physiological and plant architectural implications.* pp. 24-40.
8. Sandhu MS, Kaur R, Bal JS (2024) Studies on Floral Bud Development and Flowering

- Behaviour of Guava (*Psidium guajava* L.). *Int. J. Pharm. Pharmaceu. Sci.* 6(1): 38-43.
<https://www.ijfmr.com/papers/2024/1/11404.pdf>
9. Seth JN (1962) Floral biology studies in *Psidium guajava* L. anthesis and dehiscence of anthers, pollen studies, receptivity, fertilization and fruit setting. *Hort. Adv.* 6: 110-136.
 10. Sharma S, Sehrawat SK, Sharma S, Sharma KD (2013) Impact of environment on time of anthesis, dehiscence and stigma receptivity of guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) under semi-arid region of India. *Ann. Biol.* 29(3): 257- 263.
 11. Sharma S, Sehrawat SK, Sharma KD (2017) Studies on time and duration of flowering, floral bud development and morphology of guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) under semi-arid region of India. *Int. J. Curr. Microbiol. App. Sci.* 6(12): 4176-4186.
 12. Tandel YN, Jadav HM, Patel N (2024) Pollen morphological research of guava cultivars under South Gujarat condition. *Genetic Resources and Crop Evolution* (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10722-024-02250-6>
 13. Tanmoy S, Sarkar SK, Sarkar T, Sau S (2016) Growth and yield of guava (*Psidium guajava* L.) varieties under West Bengal condition. *Int. J. Agric. Sci.* 8(61): pp. 3499-3501.
 14. Vishwakarma PK, Vincent L, Vasugi C, Rajasekharan PE (2021) Effect of cryopreservation on pollen viability, fertility and morphology of different *Psidium* species. *Cryobiology.* 98: 112-118.
 15. Wilkie JD (2009) Interaction between the vegetative flush, flowering and yield of macadamia nut (*M. integrifolia* x *M. tetraphylla*) in a canopy management context. *Thesis Ph.D.*, University of New England. pp. 14-27.